

A RAPID REVIEW OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ACCEPTANCE AND COMMITMENT THERAPY (ACT) IN PATIENTS WITH NURSING ISSUES OF SENSORY PERCEPTION DISORDERS: HALLUCINATION

Iceu Amira^{1*}, Hendrawati Hendrawati², Aat Sriati³

^{1,2,3}*Faculty Of Nursing Padjadjaran University Jatinangor*

**Corresponding author: amira@unpad.ac.id*

Abstract

Introduction: a person's sensory perception, without any stimuli in the form of responses from the five senses, is accompanied by signs of behavioral symptoms that do not align with reality. One of the therapies that can be applied to patients with hallucinations is Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT). **Objective:** This study aims to determine the effectiveness of implementing ACT on patients with nursing problems related to sensory perception disturbances: hallucinations. **Method:** Using a rapid literature review. Article searches were conducted on several databases, namely Pubmed, ScienceDirect, Scopus, and EBSCO. For articles, several inclusion criteria were used, such as articles published in the last 10 years and written in English. The articles used are full-text articles and can be accessed for free. After conducting a screening through several stages, 5 articles were obtained that met the criteria and could be used as literature review material. **Results:** From all the articles received, it was shown that there is a significant improvement between the administration of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT), which can provide reduction/improvement in patients with hallucinations. **Conclusion:** Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) has a significant effect in reducing hallucination symptoms. Further research is expected to evaluate the long-term impact of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) on patients with hallucinations, including the sustainability of psychological flexibility and coping skills.

Keywords: Hallucinations, Acceptance and Commitment Therapy, Hallucination Symptoms.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mental disorders are changes in mental functions that cause disturbances in mental functions, leading to suffering for individuals and/or obstacles in fulfilling social roles (Lubis et al., 2014). WHO estimates that there were 970 million people worldwide with mental disorders in 2017, with an estimated 1 in 7 people having one or more mental disorders (WHO, 2018) (Ahmalia et al., 2020). The Basic Health Research (Riset Kesehatan Dasar (Riskesdas), 2018) stated that the prevalence of schizophrenia in Indonesia reached 6.7 per 1,000 population, an increase from 2013 which was 1.7 per 1,000 population (Glennasius & Ernawati, 2023). Schizophrenia is a commonly encountered and multifactorial mental disorder, its development is influenced by positive, negative, and cognitive deficit symptoms. Positive and negative symptoms are the two categories of symptoms associated with schizophrenia. Delusions, illusions, and hallucinations are examples of good symptoms; on the other hand, persistent depression, lack of drive, and apathy are examples of negative symptoms. (Bayu & Fatimah, 2023). The causes of mental disorders in an individual can be multifactorial. Still, generally, they are divided into two categories: predisposing factors and precipitating factors, which include biological, psychological, and social aspects. Factors that predispose the occurrence of mental disorders include a history of previous mental disorders, a closed personality type, unpleasant experiences, and lifelong conflicts. Meanwhile, the precipitation factor is often due to excessive stressors with poor coping mechanisms and the condition of drug withdrawal (Rinawati & Alimansur, 2016). According to

Rusdi (1998) in (Lubis et al., 2014), it is stated that there are various types of mental disorders, including organic and symptomatic mental disorders, schizophrenia, schizotypal and delusional disorders, mood disorders, neurotic disorders, somatoform disorders, behavioral syndromes associated with physiological and physical factors, personality and behavioral disorders in adulthood, mental retardation, psychological developmental disorders, and behavioral and emotional disorders with onset in childhood and adolescence. One of the mental disorders with a significant percentage is sensory perception disturbances: hallucinations, which are included in schizophrenia. Hallucinations are defined as a disturbance in a person's sensory perception, in the absence of any stimulus (Nadzifatul Laila Barikfi n.d.). Hallucination is defined as a disturbance in a person's sensory perception in the absence of a stimulus. In another definition, hallucination is a symptom of mental disorders in the form of sensory responses, namely vision, hearing, smell, touch, and taste to non-existent sources (Keliat, 2014). Patients with mental illnesses may experience hallucinations as one of the symptoms of sensory perception abnormalities. Without a genuine stimulus, the patient experiences feelings through sight, hearing, taste, touch, or smell. Keliat (2011) dalam (Sri Laela, 2018). A disturbance in a person's sensory experience without a stimulus is called a hallucination (Oktaviani et al., 2022). The types of hallucinations are categorized according to the five senses, with variations in each client's condition. Hallucinations must be our shared focus of attention because if they are not properly addressed, they can pose a risk to the safety of the patient themselves, others, and the surrounding environment. This is because the auditory hallucinations experienced by patients often contain taunts, threats, and commands to harm themselves or others. One of the therapies used for patients with hallucinations is Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT). Hayes created the behavioral therapy known as ACT in 1986 (Hayes, 1996). By embracing all of the suffering that comes with it, ACT seeks to create a meaningful existence. The decrease in symptoms is regarded as a side effect or result rather than the primary goal. (Elita et al., 2017). Primary in contrast to raising the client's standard of living. By teaching the client to view thoughts and complicated emotions as non-threatening, this therapy transforms the client's connection with these experiences over time. Embracing and paying attention to internal experiences—such as feelings, ideas, and bodily sensations—without passing judgment or attempting to exert control over them. Helping people learn to deal with painful situations and understand emotional experiences without avoiding or defending themselves is the aim (Oktama Wardani et al., 2017). There is no effort made in the implementation of ACT; instead, acceptance strategies and commitment to experiences and associated feelings are taught, rather than any attempt to minimize, alter, avoid, or control personal experiences (Hayes, Bach & Boyd, 2011) in (Irawan, 2016). ACT improves psychological adaptability, which is crucial for people with short lifespans, such as depressed patients. (Tarisa et al., 2024). ACT is a cognitive-behavioral therapy that focuses on changing the patient's relationship with the false voices of hallucinations. This therapy can reduce the impact of schizophrenia symptoms, especially auditory hallucinations, and help patients focus more on meaningful actions. Based on this background, to support the novelty of clinical evidence regarding the effectiveness of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) in patients with sensory perception disorders: and hallucinations can be implemented, the researchers conducted a literature review related to this intervention. This study aims to review and synthesize clinical evidence regarding the effectiveness of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) in reducing symptoms in patients with sensory perception disorders: hallucinations.

2. METHODS AND ANALYSIS JOURNAL

2.1. Methods

This article uses the rapid literature review method. Article searches were conducted on several databases, namely Pubmed, Science Direct, Scopus, and Ebsco. Articles, several criteria were used, such as articles published in the last 5 years and written in English. The articles used are full-text articles and can be accessed for free. After going through several filtering stages, 5 articles were obtained that meet the criteria and can be used as literature review materials.

2.2. Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using qualitative descriptive methods. The analysis process includes the following stages:

1. Searching for journals using the specified keywords and MeSH terms
2. Screening for duplicate articles from the four journals
3. Data Reduction: Selection of journals based on inclusion criteria.
4. Elimination of data that does not align with the research population's objectives
5. Collection of selected articles organized in a table to facilitate the interpretation of findings.

Figure 1. Prisma Flow Diagram

3. RESULT

The results of the articles obtained from the literature review on 4 databases, namely PubMed, EBSCO Medline, Scopus, and ScienceDirect, found 5 articles that are relevant to the theme and purpose of the EBP writing. The articles obtained from the literature review on 4 databases, namely PubMed, EBSCO Medline, Scopus, and ScienceDirect, found 5 articles that align with the theme and objectives of the EBP writing. The research findings from the 5 articles originated from the countries of Egypt, Australia, England, the United States, the Netherlands, Belgium, and Indonesia. Specifically, 2 articles discuss the effects of ACT on patients with hallucinations, and 3 articles discuss the influence of ACT on patients with psychosis (hallucinations and delusions). Based on the results from all the articles obtained, show that there is a significant improvement in patients with hallucinations through the administration of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT).

Table 1. Journal Extraction

No	Writer Country	Title/ Year	Research Objectives	Population	Data Collection	Research Design	Result
1.	Ayman Mohamed El Ashry, Egypt	Effect Of Applying "Acceptance And Commitment Therapy" On Auditory Hallucinations Among Patients With Sdchizophrenia 2021	To determine the effects of applying acceptance and commitment therapy commitment to auditory hallucinations among patients with schizophrenia.	A random sample of 70 male inpatients with schizophrenia were selected and evenly divided into study and control groups (35 patients in each group).Both groups were matched as closely as possible in terms of socio-demographic and clinical data.	Data was obtained through 2 assessment instruments, including the Psychotic Symptom Rating Scale (PSYRATS-AHs) and Voice Acceptance and Action Scale (VAAS)	This research uses aquasi-experimental research design.	The results of this study found that significant differences were observed between the study and control groups immediately after and after 3 months of ACT on the initial PSYRATS & VAAS scores.After 3 months, significant improvements in auditory hallucinations were found in the study group, as well as a decrease in readmission rates and an increase in medication adherence for the study group. compared to the control group.
2.	Frances Shawyer, John Farhall, Neil Thomas, Steven C Hayes, Robert Gallop, David	Acceptance and commitment therapy for psychosis: randomised controlled trial 2017	Evaluating the effectiveness of therapy Acceptance and Commitment (ACT) for individuals with chronic medication-resistant psychotic symptoms.	This study involve patients living in the community aged 18-65 years diagnosed with schizophrenia or schizoaffective disorder. Participants must	Various instruments were used, namely the Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (PANSS), the Psychotic Symptom Rating Scale (PSYRATS), and the Social Functioning Scale (SFS) to evaluate symptom and	This research uses a design single-blind randomized controlled trial (RCT) prospective,	This study found that ACT showed an increased effect on reducing hallucinations compared to the control group, but there were no significant effects on overall mental state or delusions.

		functional outcomes.	
Copolov, David J Castle Australia	showing hallucinations or delusion that causes stress or significant impairment, with symptoms appearing continuously for at least six months while using therapeutic doses of antipsychotic medication	psikososial	comparing two groups: the ACT intervention group and the control group

3.	Andrew Gumleya, RossWhite, Andy Briggs,Ian Fordd, Sarah Barry, orinna Stewart, Sara Beedie, Jacqueline McTaggart, Caoimhe Clarke, Rachel MacLeod ,Emma Lidstone, Bruno Salgado Riveros, Robin Young, Hamish McLeod Inggri	A parallel group randomised open blinded evaluation of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy for depression after psychosis: Pilot trial outcomes (ADAPT) 2017	To evaluate the initial effectiveness of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) in overcoming distress after experiencing psychosis	There are 29 participants who meet the criteria of being over 16 years old, fulfilling the DSM-IV-TR criteria for schizophrenia and major depression, and on antipsychotic medication.Total participants were divided into two groups, namely the intervention group (ACT + Standard Care) consisting of 15 people and the control group (Standard Care) consisting of 14 people	Data collection was conducted using the Calgary Depression Scale for Schizophrenia (CDSS) and Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) to measure the level of depression and Interview based on the Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-IV (SCID-I)	This study uses Randomised Open Blinded Evaluation (PROBE).	The results of this study found that in the CDSS category, there was no significant difference between the two groups (p=0.45).Meanwhile, on the BDI (Beck Depression Inventory) scores of the patients, there was a significant decrease in the intervention group comparec to the control group (p=0.18).
----	---	--	--	--	---	---	---

4.	Brandon A Gaudiano, Stacy Ellenberg, Jennifer E Johnson, Kim T Mueser, Ivan W Miller Amerika Serikat	Effectiveness of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy for Inpatients with Psychosis: Implementation Feasibility and Acceptability from a Pilot Randomized Controlled Trial 2023	The purpose of this study is to explore the feasibility and acceptance of the ACT intervention for psychotic patients, compared to the condition of time and attention-matched supportive therapy (TAM), as well as to evaluate the fidelity of intervention delivery by staff as part of the inpatient setting, the acceptance of study procedures, and patient satisfaction with ACT-IN and TAM	.Population in this study consists of 46 participants who have a DSM-5 diagnosis of schizophrenia spectrum disorders or mood disorders. Participants were recruited from the adult inpatient unit at a large mental health hospital in the northeastern US.	The scale used to collect data in this study includes: 1. Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale (BPRS) - the main scale for measuring psychiatric symptoms. 2. Clinical Outcomes in Routine Evaluation (CORE) - a scale to measure psychological distress. 3. World Health Organization Disability Assessment Schedule-II (WHODAS-II) - scale to measure functional impairment. 4. Quality of Life Scale (QLS) - a scale to measure specific	Pilot Randomized Controlled Trial	The research results show that ACT-IN can be well implemented by hospital staff and accepted by patients. Patients who received ACT-IN reported higher satisfaction levels compared to the group receiving time and attention-matched therapy (TAM). Furthermore, although both groups showed significant improvement in psychiatric symptoms such as hallucinations, functioning, and mindfulness during the 4-month follow-up period, only the ACT-IN group showed improvement in distress. The TAM group had a 3.76 times higher risk of rehospitalization compared to the ACT-IN group during the follow-up period.
----	--	--	---	---	---	-----------------------------------	---

psychosocial functioning for schizophrenia.
 5. Acceptance and Action Questionnaire-II (AAQ-II) - scale to measure psychological flexibility.
 6. Cognitive and Affective Mindfulness Scale-Revised (CAMS-R) scale to measure mindfulness.
 7. Valuing Questionnaire (VQ) - scale to measure the consistency of actions with personal values
 8. Client Satisfaction Questionnaire-8 (CSQ-8) - skala to measure satisfaction and acceptance of

the treatment.
9. Credibility
and
expectancy
Questionnaire
(CEQ) - scale
to measure
hope for
treatment

5.	Yanuar Fahrizal Novy Helena hatarina Daulima Mustikasar Indonesia	Applicatuin of Acceptance Commitment Therapy in Schizoaffectiv e Patients With Hallucinations And Self-Care Deficits 2021	This research aims to describe cases of medication- induced hallucinations and self-care deficits in schizoaffective patients using ACT	The sample consists of one patient with inclusion criteria who experiences schizoaffective disorder with sensory perception disturbances, hallucinations, and deficits in self-care and receiving ACT	The patient received treatment in the form of acceptance and commitment therapy over four sessions.	observatio n al design on one patient	Before ACT therapy: Poor self-perception, inability to focus thoughts, state, floating ideas, feeling constrained/bound, sad, difficulty sleeping, indifferent to the environment, inability to maintain a conversation. After ACT therapy: unable to focus thoughts, state, ideas drifting, indifferent to the environment It seems there is no text provided for translation. Please share the text you'd like me to translate, and I'll be happy to help There is a reduction in hallucination symptoms and self-care deficits after receiving acceptance commitment therapy. Acceptance commitment therapy can reduce the symptoms of sensory perception disturbances, hallucinations, and self-care deficits in schizoaffective patients.
----	--	---	--	---	--	---	---

4. DISCUSSION

Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) is a mindfulness-based therapeutic approach that focuses on accepting personal experiences without judgment and committing to actions aligned with values that are meaningful to the individual. ACT's objective of encouraging psychological adaptability in each person was accomplished. According to Bennett and Oliver (2019), psychological flexibility is the state in which people are completely aware of the circumstances, alter their behavior, or put up defenses to attain life's values. (Nasution, 2023). Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) is a mindfulness-based therapeutic approach that focuses on accepting personal experiences without judgment and committing to act by values that are meaningful to the individual. In the context of nursing, ACT has shown effectiveness in handling patients with sensory perception disorders such as hallucinations. These disorders are often rooted in the patient's inability to distinguish between external reality and internal experiences, which can exacerbate psychological distress (Hayes et al., 2012) (Sriandi, n.d.). The application of ACT to patients with hallucinations aims to enhance psychological flexibility, which is the ability to accept internal experiences (such as hallucinations) without becoming emotionally involved or trying to suppress those experiences. Through mindfulness practice, patients are encouraged to recognize that hallucinations are part of their experience without overreacting. This process helps reduce the intensity of negative emotions that often arise due to hallucinations, such as fear or anxiety. Face-to-face (offline) interactions between the client and the therapist might take place in groups or individually in ACT. (Angela & Tondok, 2021). Studies show that ACT can also enhance patients' ability to recognize meaningful life values, thereby encouraging them to engage in activities that support psychological well-being. For example, patients are encouraged to focus on their life goals even while experiencing hallucinations, rather than just trying to eliminate those symptoms. This has a positive impact on the patient's quality of life. The success of ACT in patients with sensory perception disorders also lies in the collaborative and non-confrontational nature of the therapy. This approach avoids stigma towards the experience of hallucinations, thereby helping to create a positive therapeutic relationship between the nurse and the patient. Thus, ACT is not only effective in reducing the negative impact of hallucinations but also strengthens the patient's adaptive coping skills in dealing with the disorder. Overall, the application of ACT in nursing for patients with hallucinations provides a holistic approach, helping patients to accept their experiences, reduce psychological distress, and lead a more meaningful life despite facing sensory perception disturbances (Hayes et al., 2012) in (Sriandi, n.d.) Research results indicate that acceptance and commitment therapy (ACT) can successfully reduce the severity of all aspects of auditory hallucinations in schizophrenia patients, particularly those related to distress associated with the voices. Additionally, ACT is also very promising in changing patients' responses to auditory experiences from engagement with good voices and resistance to bad voices to an attitude of acceptance and independent autonomous actions, which enables schizophrenia patients to better cope with auditory hallucinations. Furthermore, according to other researchers, the improvement reflects the treatment's focus on positive symptoms; however, the lack of changes in process measures indicates that the ACT intervention used did not manipulate the targeted processes beyond friendship. Therapeutic improvements specific to symptoms, better process investigations, as well as attention to cognitive function and dosage, are needed in future research. (Shawyer et al., 2017), The results of this study found that in the CDSS category, there was no significant difference between the two groups ($p=0.45$). The research results show that ACT-IN can be well implemented by hospital staff and accepted by patients. Patients who received ACT-IN reported higher satisfaction levels compared to the group receiving time and attention-matched therapy (TAM). Furthermore, although both groups showed significant improvement in psychiatric symptoms such as hallucinations, functioning, and mindfulness during the 4-month follow-up period, only the ACT-IN group showed improvement in distress. The TAM group had a 3.76 times higher risk of rehospitalization compared to the ACT-IN group during the follow-up period. (Gaudio et al., 2023). ACT is the most efficient way to manage psychotic symptoms to promote positive transformation, improve patient quality of life, boost drug adherence, and lower future medical expenses. (Yoduke et al., 2023). According to the results of other studies, ACT is the most efficient way to manage psychotic symptoms to promote positive transformation, improve patient quality of life, boost drug adherence, and lower future medical expenses. (Sofwan et al., 2024). ACT is the most efficient way to manage psychotic

symptoms to promote positive transformation, improve patient quality of life, boost drug adherence, and lower future medical expenses. (Maulia et al., 2022).

5. CONCLUSION

Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) has a significant effect in reducing hallucination symptoms. Further research is expected to evaluate the long-term impact of Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) on patients with hallucinations, including the sustainability of psychological flexibility and coping skills.

REFERENCES

- Ahmalia, R., Tinggi, S., Kesehatan, I., Tongga, N., Alung, L., Barat, S., & Artikel, I. (2020). *JURNAL MSSB : Medisains STIKes Sumatera Barat 1(1) 2020 : 26-32*. 1(1), 26–32.
- Angela, I., & Tondok, M. S. (2021). Efektivitas Penerapan Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) : Sebuah Tinjauan Sistematis A Systematic Review: Effectiveness of the Implementation of Commitment Therapy (ACT). *Jurnal Psikogenesis*, 9(2), 172–185.
- Bayu, S. R. A., & Fatimah, W. N. (2023). Mengontrol gangguan persepsi sensori dengan aktivitas yang terjadwal. *JKJ: Persatuan Perawat Nasional Indonesia*, 11(1), 11–18.
- Elita, Y., Sholihah, A., & Sahiel, S. (2017). Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) Bagi Penderita Gangguan Stress Pasca Bencana. *Jurnal Konseling dan Pendidikan*, 5(2), 97–101. <https://doi.org/10.29210/117800>
- Gaudio, B. A., Ellenberg, S., Johnson, J. E., Mueser, K. T., & Miller, I. W. (2023). Effectiveness of acceptance and commitment therapy for inpatients with psychosis: Implementation feasibility and acceptability from a pilot randomized controlled trial. *Schizophrenia Research*, 261, 72–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.schres.2023.09.017>
- Glennasius, T., & Ernawati, E. (2023). Program Intervensi Dalam Upaya Peningkatan Pengetahuan dan Keteraturan Berobat Pasien Skizofrenia di Wilayah Kerja Puskesmas Sindang Jaya. *Malahayati Nursing Journal*, 5(12), 4239–4249. <https://doi.org/10.33024/mnj.v5i12.12528>
- Irawan, E. (2016). Pengaruh Terapi Penerimaan dan Komitmen (Acceptance dan Commitment Therapy) Pada Penurunan Nilai Bprs Pada Pasien dengan Gangguan Sensori Persepsi : Halusinasi. *Jurnal Ilmu Keperawatan*, IV(2), 77–84.
- Lubis, N., Krisnani, H., & Fedryansyah, M. (2014). Pemahaman Masyarakat Mengenai Gangguan Jiwa Dan Keterbelakangan Mental. *Share : Social Work Journal*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.24198/share.v4i2.13073>
- Maulia, E., Novitayani, S., & Dineva, F. (2022). Acceptance And Commitment Therapy Pada Pasien Halusinasi Pendengaran: Suatu Studi Kasus. *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa*, 1(2), 125–131.
- Nadzifatul Laila Barikfi¹, A. G. (n.d.). *SENSORY PERCEPTION DISORDERS : HEARING HALLUCINATIONS*.
- Nasution, A. M. N. (2023). Review Literatur : Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (Teori dan Aplikasi). *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan, Psikologi Dan Kesehatan (J-P3K)*, 4(2), 91–98.
- Oktama Wardani, R., Agustani, H., & Elsari Novianti, L. (2017). Penerapan Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (Act) Untuk Menurunkan Derajat Stres Pengasuhan. *Jurnal Intervensi Psikologi (JIP)*, 9(2), 187–205. <https://doi.org/10.20885/intervensipsikologi.vol9.iss2.art4>
- Oktaviani, S., Hasanah, U., & Utami, I. T. (2022). Penerapan terapi Menghardik Dan Menggambar pada Pasien Halusinasi Pendengaran. *Journal Cendikia Muda*, 2(September), 407–415.
- Rinawati, F., & Alimansur, M. (1970). Analisa Faktor-Faktor Penyebab Gangguan Jiwa Menggunakan Pendekatan Model Adaptasi Stres Stuart. *Jurnal Ilmu Kesehatan*, 5(1), 34. <https://doi.org/10.32831/jik.v5i1.112>

- Riset Kesehatan Dasar (Riskesdas). (2018). Laporan Riskesdas 2018 Nasional.pdf. In *Lembaga Penerbit Balitbangkes* (hal. hal 156).
- Shawyer, F., Farhall, J., Thomas, N., Hayes, S. C., Gallop, R., Copolov, D., & Castle, D. J. (2017). Acceptance and commitment therapy for psychosis: Randomised controlled trial. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 210(2), 140–148. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.bp.116.182865>
- Sofwan, M., Nurahman, A., & Nugroho, A. (2024). *Pengaruh Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) Terhadap Tanda dan Gejala Pada Pasien Halusinasi Pendengaran di RSJD Dr Arif Zinudin Surakarta*.
- Sri Laela, at al. (2018). *Buku Ajar Keperawatan jiwa*. PENERBIT: PT Nuansa Fajar Cemerlang, Cetakan Pertama: Oktober, 2024
- Sriandi, A. K. (n.d.). *Library Research : Konseling Berbasis Acceptance and Commitment Therapy Sebagai Pencegahan dan Intervensi untuk Gangguan Kesehatan Mental LIBRARY RESEARCH : KONSELING BERBASIS ACCEPTANCE AND COMMITMENT THERAPY SEBAGAI PENCEGAHAN DAN INTERVENSI UNTUK GANGG.*
- Tarisa, J., Sriati, A., Profesi Ners, P., Keperawatan, F., Padjadjaran, U., & Jiwa, D. (2024). Penerapan Acceptance and Commitment Therapy Terhadap Halusinasi Pendengaran Pada Pasien Major Depressive Disorder: a Case Report. *Jurnal Riset Ilmiah*, 3(8), 3983–3995.
- Yoduke, F., Daulima, N. H. C., & Mustikasari, M. (2023). Acceptance and Commitment Therapy pada Pasien Skizofrenia dengan Halusinasi. *Journal of Telenursing (JOTING)*, 5(2), 3540–3548. <https://doi.org/10.31539/joting.v5i2.6112>